

Social

EDUCATIONAL PAGES IN FACEBOOK - A STUDY

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Abstract

Facebook Pages are a great resource for educational technology professionals to find companies, thought leaders, groups and organizations to share ideas and experiences with peers while expanding industry knowledge and increasing connections. Like most Facebook users, many educators use Facebook to connect with friends new and old, but the Internet's most popular site can also be a great learning and teaching tool. There are many Facebook pages that have been created as a resource to collect, share, and disseminate information about education and education technologies. In this study an attempt has been made to know about various educational pages in Facebook. The study has taken one day survey of total no. of likes and followers for educational pages in Facebook. The educational pages are identified by the Researcher based on her explorative knowledge on the field by random browsing in the Facebook. The collected data gives us an idea about teachers who use Facebook for educational purposes. This study will motivate other teachers also to browse Facebook for enhancement of their teaching and learning skills. The modern social media could be best used for maximizing teacher's personality, creative thoughts, innovative ideas and teaching competency.

Keywords: Facebook; Educational Pages.

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1. Introduction

Facebook is an American for-profit corporation and an online social media and social networking service based in Menlo Park, California. The Facebook website was launched on February 4, 2004, by Mark Zuckerberg, along with fellow Harvard College students and roommates, Eduardo Saverin, Andrew McCollum, Dustin Moskovitz, and Chris Hughes. Facebook Pages are a great resource for educational technology professionals to find companies, thought leaders, groups and organizations to share ideas and experiences with peers while expanding industry knowledge and increasing connections. Like most Facebook users, many educators use Facebook to connect with friends new and old, but the Internet's most popular

site can also be a great learning and teaching tool. There are many Facebook pages that have been created as a resource to collect, share, and disseminate information about education and education technologies.

2. Terms and Definitions

- Facebook - refers to online social media and social networking service.
- Educational Pages - refers to pages in Facebook on the aspects of Education.

3. Objectives of the Study

The study has formulated the following objectives:

- 1) To find out the number of likes for educational pages in Facebook.
- 2) To find out the number of followers for educational pages in Facebook.

4. Hypotheses Formulated for the Study

The hypotheses have been stated in null form:

- 1) There are unlimited numbers of people who like educational pages in Facebook.
- 2) There are unlimited numbers of people who follow educational pages in Facebook.

5. Sample Design

The investigator has followed probability sampling method for the present study. The investigator has collected data on 30.06.2017.

6. Educational Pages in Facebook

The numbers of people who like educational pages in Face book are presented in the following table with maximum number of people at the top and the minimum number of people at the bottom in Table 1.

HYPOTHESIS 1:

There are unlimited numbers of people who like educational pages in Facebook.

Table 1: Numbers of People Who Like Educational Pages in Facebook

S.No	Name of the FB Page	Likes
1	Clever classroom	8,77,129
2	We are teachers	8,07,409
3	Facebook in education	6,70,358
4	education.com	6,12,767
5	Scholastic Teachers	4,63,059
6	Free technology for teachers	4,42,882
7	Teaching ideas	3,09,925
8	Education to the core	3,06,589
9	Tinker lab	3,03,017

10	What the teacher wants	2,14,521
11	Educational Insights	2,02,174
12	Red ted art	1,89,898
13	Edutopia	1,88,682
14	Teacher lists	1,87,343
15	Busy teacher	1,41,922
16	Irresistible ideas for play based Learning	1,34,394
17	The corner stone for teachers	1,34,270
18	Teach hub	94,708
19	Huff post education	72,429
20	Educational Technology	59,266
21	Love, teach	38,139
22	Education world	25,842
23	The educators spin on it	20,359
24	Inclusive Class	12,913
25	Math game time	5,876
26	Math Chimp	1,109
27	Word game time	198

It is evident from Table 1 that the Facebook pages ‘Clever classroom’ and ‘We are teachers’ have more than 8 lakhs likes. ‘Teaching ideas’, ‘Education to the core’ and ‘Tinker lab’ have more than 3 lakhs likes. ‘What the Teacher wants’ and ‘Educational Insights’ have more than 2 lakhs likes. ‘Red ted Art’, ‘Edutopia’, ‘Teacher lists’, ‘Busy Teacher’, ‘Irresistible ideas for play based learning’ and ‘The corner stone’ for teachers have more than 1 lakh likes. The pages ‘Teach hub’, ‘Huff post education’, ‘Educational technology’, ‘Love, Teach’, ‘Education world’, ‘The educators spin on it’, ‘Inclusive class’, ‘math game time’, ‘Math chimp’, ‘Word game time’ have less than 1 lakh likes.

HYPOTHESIS 2:

There are unlimited numbers of people who follow educational pages in Facebook.

Table 2: Numbers of People Who Like Educational Pages in Facebook

S.No	Name of the FB Page	Followers
1	We are teachers	7,83,950
2	Scholastic Teachers	4,46,738
3	Tinker lab	2,92,664
4	What the teacher wants	2,09,910
5	Educational Insights	1,98,476
6	Teacher lists	1,84,166
7	Busy teacher	1,38,290
8	The corner stone for teachers	1,31,237
9	Irresistible ideas for play based Learning	1,23,418
10	Teach hub	92,861
11	Huff post education	70,591
12	Educational Technology	58,233

13	Love, teach	37,817
14	Education world	25,192
15	Inclusive Class	11,936
16	Math game time	5,618
17	Math Chimp	1,099
18	Word game time	197

It is evident from Table 2 that 'We are teachers' have more than 7 lakh followers in Facebook. 'Scholastic teachers' have more than 4 lakh followers. 'Tinker Lab' and 'What the teacher wants' have more than 2 lakh followers. The pages 'Educational Insights', 'Teacher Lists', 'Busy teacher', 'The Corner stone for teachers' and 'irresistible ideas for play based learning' have more than 1 lakh followers. 'Teach hub', 'Huff post education' and 'Educational Technology' have more than 50,000 followers. 'Love, Teach' and 'Education World' have more than 25,000 followers. The pages 'Inclusive Class', 'Math game time,' and 'Math chimp' have less than 15,000 followers. The page 'Word game time' is having less than 200 followers.

7. Conclusion

The study can be concluded by stating the following. They are:

- 1) The findings reveal that the Facebook pages 'Clever classroom' and 'We are teachers' have more than 8 lakhs likes. 'Teaching ideas', 'Education to the core' and 'Tinker lab' have more than 3 lakhs likes. 'What the Teacher wants' and 'Educational Insights' have more than 2 lakhs likes. 'Red ted Art', 'Edutopia', 'Teacher lists', 'Busy Teacher', 'Irresistible ideas for play based learning' and 'The corner stone' for teachers have more than 1 lakh likes.
- 2) The findings bring out the fact that the educational page 'We are teachers' have more than 7 lakh followers in Facebook. 'Scholastic teachers' have more than 4 lakh followers. 'Tinker Lab' and 'What the teacher wants' have more than 2 lakh followers. The pages 'Educational Insights', 'Teacher Lists', 'Busy teacher', 'The Corner stone for teachers' and 'irresistible ideas for play based learning' have more than 1 lakh followers.

8. Educational Implications

The study has come out with interesting finding that more than 8 lakhs people have likes for educational pages. There is same no. of people as followers for educational pages in Facebook. It gives us an idea that teachers can have more groups like this to share their ideas on education. Teachers can exhibit their classroom practices to others through this Facebook. It links teachers across the world. The teachers who have innovative ideas can share it with others. The teachers who want to be creative in the class always can have more ideas from these pages. It naturally enhances the professional competency of teachers. The finding reveals that the Facebook pages 'Clever classroom' and 'We are teachers' have more than 8 lakhs likes. It means that there are more interesting aspects in these pages for teachers. The educational page 'We are teachers' have more than 7 lakh followers in Facebook. IT clearly indicates that many new things for the teachers might be plenty in this page so that more than 7 lakh teachers have subscribed to this page. This study brings out the fact that teachers do actively use Facebook for educational purposes. Facebook helps teachers to build strong professional friendship across the globe.

Facebook makes teachers get more knowledge about teaching and learning aspects. Facebook makes classroom more vibrant.

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